

FUNCTIONING OF JAMIUL ULOOM MADRASA POKHARIPUT, BHUBANESWAR: A CASE STUDY

Rihana Parween Begum,

M. Phil in Education Fakir Mohan University Balasore.

Sarada Mishra,

M. Phil in Education Utkala University Vanibihar Bhubaneswar.

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Abstract

The term 'Madrasa' originated from Arabic language literary speaking it means a place where teaching and learning takes place. In Arabic speaking regions, any institutions that are involved in imparting education to the masses including religious institutions are usually denoted as Madrasas. The madrasa is an educational site that plays an important role in Islam education. In the medieval period after completion of primary education in the maktab the Muslim students used to go to the madrasa for their higher education. Education brings emancipation from the darkness of ignorance and populate and individual personality with the versatility of knowledge, skill and abilities in an education system, enthusiasm for learning and clarity in teaching multiply the success of what is a genuine desire of students and the objective of an institution. The researcher conducted a study on functioning of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar A case study. The study conducted with the following objectives are to study the management system of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar .To study the physical/infrastructural facilities of Jamiul Uloom Madrasah, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar. To study the learning process of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar and to study the perception of stakeholders are teacher and students of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput ,Bhubaneswar. Fifty students, eight teachers were selected through a Purposive sampling technique and data was collected through a self-developed observation schedule and Focus group discussion schedule. A thick description and micro analysis of data resulted that the Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar management system is democratic

innature,adequate infrastructural facilities are provided, learner-centered approach was followed in classroom transaction, a cordial teacher-taught relationship was developed, task analysis, story telling, group discussion method and other co-curricular activities like Milad(seminar) Zalsa(conference) are smoothly organized by the stakeholders of the Jamiul Uloom Madrasa,Pokhariput,Bhubaneswar .The headmaster of the institution is always ready and friendly to discuss anything regarding their madaras Improvement with their staff, teachers, community and students.

Key Word: *Madrasa, case study*

1. Introduction

India is country of unity in diversity which is a significant feature of India, Islamic education and madrasa have been very important part of the Muslim societies. Madrasa have been not only the centers of learning but instrumental in bringing up wider socio economic and political developments in the society as well as the Systematic and scholarly application of the scientific method interpreted in its broader sense, to the solution of educational problems, conversely any systematic study design to promote the development. The madrasa is an educational site place an important role in Islam education. In medieval period after completion of primary education in the maktab the Muslim used to go to the madrasa for their higher education. Before going to the nuances of madam and Islamic education in the Muslim societies, one need to educate oneself about Islam and its approach towards significance of education in a broader canvas of knowledge production. Madrasa is an Arabic word meaning here by an institution where students are taught. It also means a school, college or university. But now-a-days madrasa education has become an institution of purely Islamic teachings where the syllabus is mainly confined with the Qur'an and Hadith. Main objectives of madrasa to spread the message of Islam primarily among muslims and to all the other sects as muslims believed that it is the only true religion on the face of earth and it is from Almighty of ALLAH or to maintain Islamic culture among the muslims and for those who are not practicing by nature by birth. Qur'an is word of ALLAH.

2. Review of related literature

Bashori et al (1) Conducted a study on "construct management of Islamic education institutions in Indonesia: A literature review ". This study aimed to find out the solution in managing conflict in Indonesia Islamic education institutions. This study applied qualitative research data collected through a documentation library. Study found that conflict management becomes very important in managing conflicts in Islamic education institutions as the

development of quality educational institutions conflict management is a solution to balance existing conflicts.

Hasibuan et al (2) Conducted a study on "The Implementation of Islamic counseling for students mental development in madrasa ". This study aimed to explore the implementation of Islamic counseling for students mental health development at the Tanjung Bali city madrasa this is a qualitative study using Interview or observation tools for data collection. This study found that Islamic counseling services have an impact in the form of students' ability to adopt at school and in the community. Assisting students in self-control when socializing the teachers to participate in offline and online training and provision of facilities in madrasa.

Hidayat (3) Conducted a study on "Post-pandemic education study :Analysis of resource opportunities and challenges of madrasa education in Indonesia " This study analyzed the resource opportunities in madrasa education. This study used descriptive analytic methodology. The study found that the impact of the application of technology is expanding and is anticipated to increase further in the future:Impact of the application of technology in education and teaching, financial, academic administration activities and in computer centers: opportunities allowed madrasa to increase in rank due to complete recorded school activity data. The chance for madrasa to immediately take more strategic policies in adjusting to the real condition of the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Karim(4) Conducted a study on "Strategy for strengthening the characteristics of students in Tsanawiyah madrasa ". This study aimed to reveal how the teachers strategy in strengthening the character of students of state Tsanawiyah madrasa, study used qualitative methods, questionnaires or Interview tools are used for data collection. Study found that can provide an understanding that the teachers strategy in strengthening the character of students is carried out by installing religious values through a personal approach, providing endless motivation, being a good role model and providing positive suggestions through habitation.

Kultsum et al (5) Conducted a study on "Comparative studies between public and private Islamic school in the era of globalization ". This study aimed to determine the impact of the education policy implementation on madrasa with the existence of regional autonomy in Indonesia. It is a qualitative study used Interview and observation schedule tools used for data collection. The study founded that explicit rules are also needed regarding the understanding of discriminatory decentralization policies especially in madrasa and other educational institutions.

Muzayanah (6) Conducted a study on "Emergency curriculum during COVID-19 Pandemic ".Study aimed to described the practice of emergency curriculum in madrasa which includes modification, invitation and learning models during the COVID-19 Pandemic. The study used a qualitative method data were collected through interviews, observations schedule, finally researcher found three major strategies followed first the emergency curriculum policy issued by government has been implemented properly by optimizing the potential of each madrasa second innovation and modification of learning were carried out by reducing learning hours determine essential material and diversity learning methods third the learning model carried out by madrasa includes online learning offline learning and limited face-to- face learning.

Nuraeni et al (7) Conducted a study on "The influence of madrasa organizational characteristics on the principal decision-making ".The study aimed to determine how big the relationship between organisational characteristics and decision- making processes of the head of the madrasa as a leader. The quantitative method used with non-experimental research methods Questionnaire were given to thirty four respondents who are teachers at madrasa Aliyah-al-Mustaqiem. The study found that application of organizational characteristics of this madrasa with the average data obtained is 3128 which means that teachers asses madrasa have often applied indicators of organizational characteristics in madrasa.

Nurbani (8) Conducted a study on "Systematic literature review (SLR)Al-Quran-Hadith subjects at madrasa, this study was based on qualitative method. Data collection is done by documentation all articles that have similar research. It was found that teacher competence plays an important role especially in designing learning and inculcating good values for students as the main target in learning the Quran Hadith namely being able to realize in everyday life.

Sakarina et al (9) Conducted a study on "strategic management of Islamic education revealing the challenges of professionalism "study explore to identify and analyzed the application strategies of management in revealing the challenges of professionalism in the digitalization era. Study used qualitative methods data collected through interviews, observations and documentation. This study founded that the strategic management of Islamic education in revealing the challenges of professionalism in the digitalization era at madrasa Ibtidaiyah madrasa based on management strategy in the digital era and carried outlined training programmes for the teachers.

Santosa and Jazuli (10) Conducted a study on "The digital madrasa as an idea of IT-Based Islamic education. Study explored to analyzed the implementation of ICT in madrasa. This study was a qualitative method used data collected through documentation method or observation method. Finally this study founded that the application of ICT is not only in the realm of madrasa governance education and educational environment that are aware that the use of technology has become a must if you want to create a digital based school synchronous approach asynchronous blended learning is an approach that can be chosen in digital learning. Sudarmanto et al (11) Conducted a study on "Duties and responsibilities of the principal of madrasa towards the teachers professionalism development ". This study proposed to described the role of the principal as a leader in developing teachers professionalism, it is a qualitative research study method data were collected through interview and observation. Finally the researcher was get three findings innovator duties of madrasa principal was developed individually professionalism teams restructuring madrasa, conducting reinforcements secondly motivator duties/responsibilities thirdly the principal of madrasa as a constructing job description and job specification, collecting all of the resources in the madrasa, assisting a capable co-ordinating and arranging programme scheduling in madrasa collaborating with other parties.

Suyanto(12) Conducted a study on "Management style of head of Aliyah state madrasa increasing motivation for achievement of educational workers in Jambi province the aimed of the study to analyzed the management style of the head of madrasa Aliyah in increasing motivation study used descriptive qualitative approach data collection with observation, interviews and documentation techniques the findings of the study are democratic style of madrasa form task direction, decision making and relationship build. A democratic climate in schools which encouraged the creation of a conducive climate for the creation of optimal quality of work. The achievement motivation of educational staff in Jambi-province is characterized by work creativity. The principal management style increasing the achievement motivation or education staff of Jambi-province is clear work direction joint decision-makings and two-way relationships.

2.1 Objectives of the Study

- (I) To Study/to find out the management system of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar.
- (II) To find out infrastructural facilities of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar.
- (III) To study the learning process of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar

2.2 Research Questions

(I) How far the management system of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar is effective.

(II) How far the human, physical and material resource facilities are adequate and relevant to meeting the needs of the learners of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar.

(III) What are the teaching learning practices taken by Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar .

3.1 Case size: The study consisted eight teachers forty five students and one headmaster of Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar located at near biju patnaik international airport, gandamunda pokhariput, Bhubaneswar of Khordha district sample of the study which were located through Purposive sampling technique. In this study the researcher was taken all the population as sample.

3.2 Data collection and data analysis: The required data was collected through administering self-developed observation schedule for madrasa and Focus group discussion to students. The tools developed by the researcher considered management system, infrastructural facilities and learning processes as the dimensions of the study. After preparation, five experts and special educators tested the content Validity of the tools. The investigator also analyzed data observed by her with thick descriptions. The Focus group discussion have been transmitted into verbatim. Microanalysis on the verbatim have been done. Manually.

4. Results and discussion: The qualitative data was analyzed with the help of content analysis qualitative content analysis involves a process designed to condense raw data into categories on themes based on valid inference and interpretation both the focus group discussion and observation schedule were administered to get the required information from the respondents. Through the observation schedule this study fulfill the objectives of the study this institute name Jamiul Uloom Madrasa, Pokhariput, Bhubaneswar district Khordha, odisha. This institution has forty five students or eight teachers and other two staff the researcher direct visit and observation that water facility ,classroom facility, kitchen shed facility, separate teachers and students toilet facility, playground facility, Boundary wall facility, garden facility, books on all subjects facilities are available here. Through the observation schedule the researcher get various information/data collected how far the material resource fulfill students' needs, Drinking facilities, sports equipment, class wise books, newspapers, magazines, moral books are available in this madrasa. Through the Focus group discussion the researcher get information about co-curricular activities in this madrasa organized Milad (semina)

Zalsa(conference) for students inner abilities should be enhanced and the students professionalism ethics should be developed so that all the students enhanced their motivational tendencies towards madrasa education.

4.1 Shortcoming of the Institution/Madrasa Adopt Better Development

- (I) Lack of competency of their teachers in using ICT.
- (II) Further researcher may undertake quantitative studies of this institution.
- (III) Study may be conducted to explain the link between Maktab and madrasa.

4.2 conclusion: The case study of the selected madrasa clearly shows that for the holistic development of an individual greater importance on students' participation in co-curricular activities, teacher taught relationships

References

- Bashori, (2022) ConstructmanagementofIslamiceducationinIndonesia:A literaturereview <https://doi.org/10.25128/2520-6230.20.1.7>.
- Hasibuan ,Lubis and budianti, (2022). The implementation of Islamic counselling for students mental development in madrasa *journalbasiceducation.6(2)2173-2179*.<https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v6i2.2320>
- Hidayat (2022), Post-pandemic education study:analysis of resource, opportunities and challenges of madrasa education in Indonesia *journal of positive school psychology vol.6 No.5(2022) 7342-7354*
- Karim, A. R., & Arifuddin. (2022). *Strategy for strengthening the characteristics of students in tsanawiyah madrasa. Pappaseng: International Journal of Islamic Literacy and Society, 1(1), 13–22. https://doi.org/10.56440/pijilis.v1i1.36*
- Kultsum1, U., & Abrar Parinduri, M. A., & Karim, A.(2022). Comparative studies between public and private Islamic schools in the era of globalizationVol. 11(1), 421~430 DOI: 10.11591/ijere.v11i1.22182
- Rahmatullah, M. (2021) MANAGEMENT STRATEGY FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF *MADRASAH* IN BANTENPROVINCE: QUALITATIVE SYSTEMATIC REVIEW. Vol. 37(05), 1410-3222 . <http://dx.doi.org/10.32678/alqalam.v38i1.4290>.
- Muzayanah, U., Muawanah, S., Wibowo, A., & Shofwan. (2022, April 25). Emergency Curriculum during COVID-19 Pandemic. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xvzyh>
- Nuraeni1, R., & Manggala, T.S., & Mutmainah, N.A, & Wulandari, R.T. (2022) The Influence of Madrasah Organizational Characteristics on the Principal Decision-Making Vol. 6

(02), 327-337 Available online at <https://ejournal.unuja.ac.id/index.php/al-tanzim/index>.

Karim , A. R, & Arifuddin (2022) Strategy for Strengthening The Characteristics of Students in madrasa of Tsanawiyah <https://ejournals-glm.id/index.php/pappaseng>

Nurbani(2022), Systematic literature review (SLR) Al-Quran- Hadith subjects at madrasa. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)Volume 5, No. 1, February 2022, Page: 521-534 e-ISSN: 2615-3076 (Online), p-ISSN: 2615-1715 (Print) www.bircu-journal.com/index.php/birci*

Sakarina, S., & Pratiwi,R,. & Surahman, S,. & Cakranegara, P.A .& Arifin. (2022). Strategic Management of Islamic Education: Revealing The Challenges of Professionalism. *Al-Tanzim: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam Vol. 06 (03) (2022),778-788* Available online at <https://ejournal.unuja.ac.id/index.php/al-tanzim/index> *Al-Tanzim: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam Vol. 06*

Santosa and Jazuli,(2022) THE DIGITAL MADRASAH AS AN IDEA OF IT-BASED ISLAMIC EDUCATION *Nazhruna: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*Vol. 5 Issue 2, 2022. pp. 379-391 E-ISSN: 2614-8013 DOI:<https://doi.org/10.31538/nzh.v5i2.2121><https://ejournal.ikhac.ac.id/index.php/NAZHRUNA/index>

Sudarmanto (2022) Duties and Responsibilities of the Principal in Madrasa towards Teachers' Professionalism Development : *JIEMAN: Journal of Islamic Educational Management*, Vol. 4 No. 1 DOI 10.35719/jieman.v4i1.91

Suyanto, s. (2022). MANAGEMENT STYLE OF HEAD OF ALIYAH STATE MADRASAH IN INCREASING MOTIVATION FOR ACHIEVEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL WORKERS IN JAMBI PROVINCE (SURVEY AT MAN 2 JAMBI CITY, MAN 2 BATANG HARI AND MAN 1 BUNGO).*Volume 3, (5), 2686-5211. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31933/dijms.v3i5>*